

PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL SYSTEM OF PREPARING FUTURE TEACHERS FOR PROFESSIONAL INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES

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Annotation: This article examined the specific pedagogical and psychological features of the process of preparing future teachers for innovative professional activities and focused on the great interest of teachers in scientific work in the field of theory and practice of pedagogical innovation.

Keywords: Professional training and understanding, future teacher, innovative professional activity, pedagogical practice, competitiveness, creative approach, pedagogical situations, innovation, modernization of the educational sphere, innovative ideas, social relations.

The main part: In the context of the fundamental reforms carried out in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to clarify the content and essence of education, to formulate its goals and objectives on the basis of the progress of reforms today. The head of our country Sh.M.Mirziyoyev's speech at the Joint Session of the House of Commons on December 14, 2016, on the occasion of the solemn inauguration of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, “we mobilize all the strength and capabilities of our state and society so that our youth have independent thinking, high intellectual and spiritual potential and become people who do not empty in any The fact that the field of training in the direction of pedagogy in our country is also approached from this point of view will undoubtedly give its bright results in the near future. As an important aspect of reforms in the educational system, issues of the upbringing of a harmonious personality were put together, the legal framework for the formation of young people as a harmonious personality was developed. In it, state laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decrees, decisions and executive-political ideas of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, state programs, decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers, regulatory and legal acts determine the content and actual tasks of reforms in education. During the years of independence, many laws, decrees, resolutions and other types of regulatory documents were adopted to protect the

social, economic, legal, political, medical, spiritual, as well as educational interests of young people. The law “on education” of the Respublika of Uzbekistan was adopted in the new edition on September 23, 2020. Article 36 of this law will be devoted to experimental and innovative activities in the field of Education. It is also envisaged that competent public administration bodies and local government bodies in the field of Education will create conditions within their competence for the implementation of innovative training programs and projects and the implementation of their results in practice.

The concept of a profession is an occupation that requires special training, a person is always experienced and serves as a resource for him to live. The profession unites people engaged in the same activity, and within this activity certain norms of communication and morality are established. In theory, it is advisable to study the problem of research, analyze and highlight the content of significant concepts, categories of social relevance. Therefore, during scientific research, an attempt was made to highlight the pedagogical and psychological aspects of professional adaptation by clarifying: motives, motives for choosing a profession, professional orientation, orientation for a pedagogical profession, pedagogical activity, skills and qualifications of professional knowledge, the essence of such concepts as competence. Professional training is the level of physiological, psychological and physical training of an individual in relation to the conduct of professional activities on the basis of special theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications, as well as mastering spiritual and moral qualities. Formation of professional training- the formation of special theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications in a person on the basis of the requirements of the DTS, as well as spiritual and moral qualities, is the process of physiological, psychological and physical training of the future specialist in relation to the successful conduct of professional activities. Professional training-professional activity of the future specialist means the assimilation, individualization of requirements.

To prepare future educators professionally and spiritually, it is necessary to enrich the content of lectures, practical and laboratory classes in the educational process on the basis of new approaches, as well as organize pedagogical practice, days and hours of spirituality using improved programs. In ensuring the effectiveness of public education, the educator is required to have an in-depth pedagogical psychological training, a clear knowledge of the specific aspects of each

student, and to strictly adhere to the following requirements when creating a personal plan:

- ✚ be able to predict the pedagogical problems that arise; for this, the future pedagogical educator must have the ability to anticipate and eliminate the problems that arise in the pedagogical process.
- ✚ mastering the methods of troubleshooting the problems that arise;
- ✚ able to choose and apply the most convenient ways to eliminate the problems that have arisen;
- ✚ to have pedagogical influence on students, to have the skill to support them;
- ✚ individual approach to each student;
- ✚ mastery of the skill of being able to organize mass events with students;
- ✚ such as encouraging readers to read and love books.

The main place in the formation of innovative competence is occupied by independent work of educators. This can be achieved by training educators in the educational process to independently solve problematic tasks and tasks. Based on this common goal, Independent Education makes teachers accustomed to applying their mental potential to Tula in any circumstances and circumstances, to seek out the necessary knowledge, to apply it to their practical activities. In a word, he prepares to act as a full-fledged, competitive specialist in social life and in the production process. The curriculum, programs and textbooks will absorb the specified educational materials. It is taught to apply in practical activities, to achieve guaranteed results. Focusing on the independent functioning of the educator as much as possible in this process will give a positive result.

Conclusion: one of the most important tasks of teachers is to help children overcome their negative characteristics, to teach them honesty and truthfulness, to strengthen their will. In this, teachers must use the zamoavi method. Teachers should introduce children to the surrounding reality and prepare them to participate in the process. Only when children are given specific, moderately complex tasks do they show initiative, interest and desire to be. As a result, the child develops a sense of responsibility and tries to justify the Trust expressed by the teacher. Being able to perform the tasks assigned to them will help children regulate their behavior.

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